

THE BURDEN DISEASE DUE TO COVID: A SECONDARY DATA ANALYSIS IN SOUTHEAST EUROPE, CENTRAL ASIA AND THE SOUTHERN CAUCASUS

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Introduction

Many countries in Southeast Europe, Central Asia and the Southern Caucasus have experienced a considerable impact from the COVID-19 pandemic, with high estimated excess mortality, though in most of these countries Burden of Disease (BoD) indicators for COVID-19 have not yet been calculated. Within the BoCO-19-study, we adapt and apply COVID-19 disease model (the 'Burden-EU' model) in order to calculate the number of Years of Life Lost due to death (YLL), the number of Years Lived with Disability (or time lost due to ill-health - YLD) and the number of Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALY – representing the sum of YLL and YLD) across 14 different countries or sub-national regions in Southeast Europe, Central Asia and the Southern Caucasus. This paper describes the process of data collection and aggregation, as well as the methodological developments and the analytical approaches used, in order to harmonize and implement the calculations across all partner countries.

Materials and Methods:

To achieve its goals, the study uses a customized data collection template to gather data on national population size as well as COVID-19 cases (data available from national surveillance systems in all countries) and deaths (data available either from surveillance systems or from national civil registration and vital statistics systems), over a minimum period of 12 months (March 2020 to February 2021). YLL are calculated as described in the Burden-EU model, using the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) 2019 aspirational life expectancy table. Additional age and sex specific all-cause mortality data is collected (for the years 2015-2019), in order calculate excess mortality estimates. For the calculation of YLD, the Burden-EU model is used as the starting point. However, the available updated evidence with regard to the post-acute consequences of COVID-19 will be reviewed, with potential adaptations to the model made for this severity grade of illness. Across all countries and sub-national regions, a uniform distribution of cases across severity grades of illness (taken from German national data on COVID-19 cases) and duration of illness taken from the literature will be applied. This is because national data for these parameters are not available in many BoCO-19 countries, and because the use of uniform values helps to minimize differences between countries in terms of health-system access and infrastructure (and thus how cases are assigned to severity grades). Results will be compared to explore and identify trends across age-groups, sexes and over time in each of the partner countries or regions.

Discussion:

The BoCO-19 study serves as a scientific network and collaborative platform, bringing together public health experts from across Europe, Central Asia and the Southern Caucasus. It builds capacity for the implementation of burden of disease methods, and enables an assessment and comparison of the burden of COVID-19 across 14 different countries or sub-

national regions. Challenges in the interpretation of the study's results include inherent differences in data collection and reporting systems between countries, as well as assumptions made during the calculations (e.g. use of a uniform severity distribution), which must be borne in mind when interpreting study results.